

Phosphate- and pH-dependent self-assembly of recombinant spider silk proteins

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Abstract

The process of molecular self-assembly is an omnipresent mechanism in nature to generate a variety of efficient and functional hierarchical architectures, and inspires tailored material design and development. Thereby, self-assembly is based on a controlled interplay and association of monomers into highly ordered structures triggered by different non-covalent interactions. However, in the context of structural protein self-assembly, this association process could be influenced by the underlying amino acid sequence as well as external triggers including pH value, protein concentration or ionic composition. Thus, understanding their impact on protein conformation and assembly is indispensable for controlled protein processing and functional material engineering. Here, we analyzed the self-assembly behavior of the intrinsically unstructured, recombinant spider silk proteins eADF4(Ω 16) and eADF4(C16), which only differing in one amino acid residue in their repetitive module (glutamine and glutamic acid, respectively), depending on the concentration of kosmotropic potassium phosphate (KPi) and the pH value. The low protein charge in eADF4(Ω 16) at neutral pH led to a compacted protein conformation and a significantly increased sensitivity to phosphate resulting in faster assembly kinetics of nanofibrils and precipitation of particles at lower KPi concentrations. In contrast, the presence of glutamic acid residues in eADF4(C16) enhanced the solubility and stability of protein monomers above physiological pH, but led to an enhanced assembly/aggregation along with decreasing pH-values. Interestingly, deprotonation of tyrosine residues at pH 10 introduced negative charges resulting in decreased hydrophobic interactions and thus, decelerated restructuring and assembly of eADF4(Ω 16). Our results enabled the identification of Pi- and pH-dependent conformation and assembly models of spider silk proteins allowing controllable processing into fibrils, particles or hydrogels for specific applications.

Introduction

Protein self-assembly is based on a controlled interaction of monomers into higher ordered structures allowing the efficient generation of hierarchical architectures in nature. The process of self-assembly is triggered by different non-covalent interactions including electrostatic, hydrophobic and van der Waals interactions as well as hydrogen bonding and aromatic stacking.¹⁻⁵ In this context, the fibril and fiber formation of structural proteins, such as collagen, elastin, keratin or silk, depends on repetitive amino acid (AA) sequences (peptide motifs) directing the non-covalent interactions.⁶⁻⁹ The respective protein sequence and/or structure requires specific stimuli, including pH, concentration, temperature and ionic conditions, for multiscale fibril formation.^{6, 10-12} For instance, collagen I contains the tri-peptide repeats Gly-X-Y, where X and Y are mostly represented by proline and hydroxyproline residues, respectively. They are responsible for the formation of helical structures leading to triple-helix assembly via hydrophobic interactions and further development of protofibrils, fibrils and fibers stabilized via intermolecular ionic and hydrogen bonding.^{7, 10, 13}

In contrast, spider silk proteins comprise larger repetitive peptide modules (30-40 AA in case of major ampullate spidroins) that are intrinsically unstructured but fold into β -sheets during assembly into solid, mechanically unique fibers combining high toughness and elasticity.¹⁴⁻¹⁹ Structural studies revealed that the amino acid composition and secondary structures of the spider silk proteins are responsible for these extraordinary mechanical fiber properties.¹⁹⁻²³ Importantly, a pH drop from 8 to 5²⁴⁻²⁶, a simultaneous decrease of the concentration of chaotropic sodium chloride and the increase of kosmotropic potassium phosphate significantly influence β -sheet formation of the spider silk proteins *in vivo* and *in vitro*.^{17, 24, 27-35} The molecular interactions within the fibers are based on hydrophobic stacking of the β -sheets into nanocrystals, which are embedded in an H-bonded amorphous matrix of unstructured regions containing β -turns, β -spirals and 3₁-helices.^{17, 19, 36-41} On the molecular level, poly-alanine-rich stretches (Ala)_n in the repetitive core

domains are self-assembling into β -sheets, while glycine- and proline-rich protein stretches (e.g. GPGXY, GXX) represent an amorphous matrix in the case of recombinant variants of engineered *Araneus diadematus* fibroin 4 (eADF4), one of at least two major ampullate spidroins of the European garden spider.^{17, 23, 42-45}

eADF4(C16) is inspired by the repetitive core domain of ADF4 and comprises 16 repeats of a consensus sequence (C-module: GSSAAAAAAAAASGPGGYGPENQGPSGPGGYGPGGP).⁴⁶

Due to one glutamic acid residue in each repetitive unit, recombinant eADF4(C16) has a negative net charge at neutral pH.^{46, 47} Previous studies indicated that kosmotropic phosphate ions (Pi) at concentrations below 300 mM trigger self-assembly of eADF4(C16) into nanofibrils at physiological pH, while Pi concentrations above 400 mM induce particle precipitation.^{11, 12, 29, 30,}

⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰ It was shown that eADF4(C16) nanofibril formation follows a primary nucleation-dependent assembly mechanism⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ and comprises an additional secondary nucleation pathway¹² (**Figure 1A**). Importantly, the assembly kinetics of the engineered variants are influenced by the number of repetitive units, protein concentration, presence of nucleation seeds, nature and concentration of kosmotropic ions, temperature, and presence of additional, distinctive peptide tags at the protein's termini (**Figure 1B**).^{11, 12, 29, 49, 50, 52} Changes in environmental conditions could be used to affect the characteristics of the fibrils^{11, 12} as well as to translate the self-assembly of the proteins in diverse applications on surfaces⁵³⁻⁵⁶ or in bulk, hydrogel-based materials^{52, 57-62}.

Figure 1. Factors influencing eADF4(C16) spider silk fibril self-assembly. **A)** eADF4(C16) follows a nucleation-dependent self-assembly process for fibril formation in presence of kosmotropic anions (e.g. Pi). In the primary nucleation phase (lag phase), intrinsically unstructured monomers (I) undergo structural transformation (anti-parallel β -sheets) (II) forming β -sheet-rich nuclei (seeds) via hydrophobic interactions (III). During the fibril elongation phase, additional monomers attach to these nuclei (seeds) and undergo restructuring, leading to fibril growth and extension (IV). Moreover, secondary nucleation occurs, as monomers interact with the surface of existing fibrils, accelerating fibril formation and promoting fibril branching (V). In the saturation phase (final plateau), fibril formation is completed (VI)^{12,50}. **B)** Summary of factors that accelerate (orange) or decelerate (blue) eADF4(C16) fibril formation^{11, 12, 29, 49, 50, 52}. The black curve

illustrates an exemplary eADF4(C16) assembly curve at RT and a protein concentration of 1 mg/ml in presence of 150 mM KPi.

A point mutation in the repetitive module allowed an exchange of glutamic acid to glutamine residues yielding the variant eADF4(Ω 16) with zero net charge at neutral conditions.^{47, 63} Correspondingly, when lysine residues are introduced, the positively charged counterpart eADF4(κ 16) was achieved.^{47, 64, 65} Interestingly, studies on hydrogel formation based on experiences with fibril self-assembly in case of eADF4(C16)^{57, 59, 66}, showed significant changes in gelation kinetics and gel stability in case of eADF4(Ω 16) and eADF4(κ 16)⁵⁸. However, the impact of single amino acid exchanges in the repetitive spider silk unit along with the protein charge on the protein folding and nanofibril self-assembly have been poorly understood, yet. Here, we studied the influence of kosmotropic phosphate ions and pH on conformational changes and self-assembly behavior of eADF4(C16) in comparison to eADF4(Ω 16).

Materials and Methods

Reagents and solutions

Experiments at different pH values were performed in the pH range from 3 to 10 with the following 50 mM buffers: pH 3 (Glycine-HCl), pH 4 and 5 (sodium acetate-NaOH), pH 6 (PIPES-NaOH), pH 7-9 (TRIS- HCl) and pH 10 (Glycine-NaOH). Ultrapure water (Milli-Q-system) was used. If not otherwise stated, all chemicals were purchased from Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, Germany).

Protein solubilisation and characterization

The engineered spider silk protein eADF4(C16) was purchased from AMSilk GmbH (Germany) as lyophilized powder. The uncharged eADF4(Ω 16) variant was produced, purified and analyzed as previously described.^{47, 63} The lyophilized proteins were dissolved in 6 M guanidinium thiocyanate and dialyzed overnight using dialysis membranes with a molecular weight (MW) cutoff of 6–8 kDa (Spectra/Por, Thermo Fisher Scientific GmbH, Germany). While eADF4(C16) was dialyzed against 5-10 mM Tris/HCl, pH 8 at room temperature, dialysis of eADF4(Ω 16) was performed using 5-10 mM Tris/HCl, pH 8 at 4°C to avoid protein aggregation.⁴⁷ Precipitates

formed during dialysis were removed by ultracentrifugation (Optima MAX-XP, Beckman-Coulter, USA) at 185,000 g at 4°C for 50 minutes. Protein concentrations were determined using an UV-VIS spectrophotometer (NanoDrop 1000, Thermo Fisher, USA).

In the following, the protein solutions were characterized at different states to determine solubility and assembly/aggregation behavior: i) immediately after ultracentrifugation at pH 8, ii) after ultracentrifugation and addition of different potassium phosphate concentrations (30-500 mM KPi), iii) after ultracentrifugation and addition of buffers with different pH values (pH 3-10), iv) after incubation in buffers with various phosphate concentrations or at different pH values.

Far-UV circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy

Far-UV CD spectroscopy was conducted between 200 and 250 nm to determine the secondary structure content of soluble, ultracentrifuged (1h, 4°C, 55,000 rpm) spider silk proteins as reported previously.^{11, 12, 47, 50} CD spectra were recorded on a J-815 CD spectrometer (Jasco, Japan) using concentrations of 0.2 mg/ml, cuvettes with a path length of 0.1 cm, an integration time of 2 s, and a scanning speed of 100 nm min⁻¹. Five spectra were recorded and averaged.

Matrix assisted laser desorption ionization with time-of-flight (MALDI-TOF) mass spectroscopy

MALDI-TOF molecular weight analysis was performed as previously described.⁴⁷ The protein solutions were treated with ZipTip C4 pipette tips (Millipore, Germany) to desalt and concentrate the proteins. Sinapinic acid-matrix (20 mg/mL in 60% acetonitrile and 0.1 % trifluoroacetic acid) was used for elution and spotting on a ground steel target plate. Spectra were recorded using a Bruker Autoflex MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometer (Bruker, Germany) equipped with a 337 nm N₂ laser in a linear mode and an acceleration voltage 20 kV.

Size exclusion chromatography coupled to multiangle light scattering (SEC-MALS)

SEC-MALS was conducted on a Superdex 200 Increase 10/300 GL-column (Cytiva, Germany) connected to an Agilent 1100 Series HPLC system with a MALS detector DAWN EOS (Wyatt, Germany) as reported previously⁵¹, to determine the molecular weights and protein sizes.

Ultracentrifuged eADF4(C16) and eADF4(Ω 16) protein solutions at concentrations of 1-3 mg/ml were applied via a 200 μ L loop at a flow rate of 0.8 ml/min. The eluted proteins were analyzed using a UV-detector at 280 nm, a refractive index detector Shodex RI-71 and a static light scattering detector DOWN EOS equipped with a K5 flow cell. Molecular masses and sizes were calculated from light scattering signals using the ASTRA 6 software (Wyatt, Germany). Data were obtained from four independent measurements for each protein.

Measurements of self-assembly/aggregation kinetics

Ultracentrifuged protein solutions (10 μ M) were monitored every 10 minutes at 27 $^{\circ}$ C using turbidity measurements at 340nm in a plate reader (SpectraMax iD5, Molecular Devices, Germany) or a UV-spectrometer (Cary 50 UV, Varian, Germany), following the addition of potassium phosphate at various concentrations (30-500 mM KPi, pH 8) or buffers with different pH values (pH 3 (Glycine-HCl), pH 4 and pH 5 (sodium acetate- NaOH), pH 6 (PIPES-NaOH), pH 7–9 (TRIS- HCl) and pH 10 (Glycine-NaOH), to determine assembly/aggregation kinetics. For analyzing eADF4(C16) fibril formation between pH 8, 9 and 10 under similar conditions, 150 mM KPi (2-fold negatively charged phosphate) were added to induce self-assembly.

Fitting the kinetic data using a sigmoidal curve

Turbidity measurements were plotted as a function of time and fitted by a sigmoidal curve using Equation 1 and Origin (OriginLab Corporation) (**Equation 1**)⁶⁷ as described by Humenik et al.⁵⁰.

$$y = y_i - m_i x + \frac{y_f - m_f x}{1 + e^{-\frac{x - x_0}{\tau}}} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

There, $y_i - m_i x$ represents the initial slope during the lag phase, $y_f - m_f x$ is the slope after the growth phase and x_0 represents the time at 50% conversion. The apparent rate constant, k_{app} , for the growth of fibrils is given by $1/\tau$, and the lag time is given by $x_0 - 2\tau$ (**Table S1**). This method enables comparison of lag times in different fibril assembly kinetics.⁶⁷

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy

FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Tensor 27 (Ettlingen, Germany) using an attenuated total reflection (ATR) sampling technique on a germanium crystal. Spider silk proteins and their

assemblies were characterized in a solid state after lyophilization. Spectra were recorded in absorbance mode at RT, with a 4 cm⁻¹ resolution in the range of 900–4000 cm⁻¹. OPUS software (version 6.5, Bruker Optik, GmbH) was used to process the data (corrected for background and atmosphere). Only Amide I-III range (1300–1800 cm⁻¹) spectra with information on protein secondary structure are shown. Fourier self-deconvolution (FSD) of the Amide I band was carried out as reported previously.^{65, 68} Data were averaged from three FSD evaluations for each protein.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

TEM was conducted as described previously.^{11, 12, 50, 58, 62} In brief, spider silk protein suspensions and assemblies were deposited on Pioloform-carbon-coated 200-mesh copper grids (Plano GmbH, Germany) and incubated for 60-120 s at room temperature. Afterwards, the solution was blotted using a fiber free paper (Kimtech Kimwipes, Kimberly-Clark), and the adsorbed samples were washed with water. After negative staining using 2% uranyl acetate for 60 s, the samples were washed again with water. The samples were dried for at least 24 h and stored in darkness until further use. Images were recorded using a Zeiss LEO EM922 Omega microscope (Zeiss Microscopy, Jena, Germany). The microscope was operated at 80 kV accelerating voltage. Images were recorded by a bottom mounted CCD camera system (Ultrascan 1000, Gatan, Muenchen, Germany) and processed with a digital imaging processing system (Digital Micrograph GMS 1.9, Gatan, Muenchen, Germany).

Results and Discussion

Influence of kosmotropic potassium phosphate on eADF4(Ω16) (at neutral pH)

The influence of different KPi concentrations (up to 500 mM KPi, pH 8) on eADF4(Ω16) assembly behavior has been investigated (**Figure 2**) in comparison to that of eADF4(C16) at 150 mM (**Figure S1**). Turbidity measurements at 340 nm revealed a higher sensitivity of eADF4(Ω16) towards kosmotropic Pi as of eADF4(C16) (**Figure 2A** vs. **Figure S1**) administered in shorter lag times and higher apparent rate constants (**Table S1A** vs. **C**).

Figure 2. Influence of potassium phosphate (KPi) on self-assembly of eADF4(Ω16) without charged amino acid residues. **A)** Normalized turbidity evolution of eADF4(Ω16) at 340 nm indicating increasing self-assembly rates with increasing KPi concentrations. Data were normalized, averaged over three replicates at each condition (n=3) and fitted to sigmoidal curves (Eq. 1). **B)** FTIR-spectra of the amide I, II and III regions indicate β-sheet-rich secondary structure content of the assembled eADF4(Ω16) structures verified by FSD analysis (Table S2). **C)** TEM showing formation of eADF4(Ω16) nanofibrils between 30 mM (i) and 150 mM KPi (iv) and particle formation beginning at 150 mM KPi (v). For comparison, TEM images of eADF4(C16) nanofibrils are shown obtained at 150 mM KPi (vi).

As shown by the kinetic data (**Table S1A**), an acceleration of eADF4(Ω 16) assembly was observed with increasing KPi concentrations (from 30 mM to 150 mM). Hence, at 150 mM KPi, self-assembly of eADF4(Ω 16) was already finished within 2h, while for eADF4(C16), the final plateau, indicating consumption of the monomers, was reached only after 33h (**Figure S1**, pH 8) at the same protein concentration.^{11, 12, 49, 50} Thus, the shorter lag phases of eADF4(Ω 16) indicated a faster structural transformation of monomers compared to eADF4(C16) (see also **Figure 1A**).

After reaching the final plateau, the eADF4(Ω 16) protein assemblies were investigated using FTIR-spectroscopy and Fourier-Self-Deconvolution (FSD) of the amide I band⁶⁸ to determine secondary structure content (**Figure 2B**, **Table S2**), and TEM to analyze morphology (**Figure 2C**). FTIR-spectra indicated β -sheet-rich secondary structure for all eADF4(Ω 16) protein assemblies independent of the KPi-concentration, since the amide I bands showed maxima at wavenumbers of around 1630 cm^{-1} (**Figure 2B**) verified by FSD-analysis of these bands indicating a β -sheet content higher than 40 % (**Table S2**).

TEM analysis allowed to distinguish between aggregates, particles and nanofibrils (**Figure 2C**), revealing that eADF4(Ω 16) self-assembled into fibrils between 30 and 150 mM KPi (**Figure 2C**, **i-iv**) corresponding with the kinetic data and the sigmoidal turbidity increase (**Figure 2A**). However, the fibril morphology varied significantly dependent on the KPi concentration. At 30 mM KPi, only short, “molten” fibrils were visible, which clustered into bigger aggregates (**Figure 2C**, **i**). Probably both pathways, the KPi-induced nucleation and self-assembly of eADF4(Ω 16) and the protein aggregation occurring commonly without KPi, were present in that case. However, 50 mM and 100 mM KPi supported the self-assembly pathway resulting in long fibrils with typical entanglements (**Figure 2C**, **ii-iii**). Hence, this KPi concentration range seemed to support the formation of seeds, ordered interaction of soluble eADF4(Ω 16) thereon and fibril elongation. Interestingly, at 150 mM KPi, only short, molten and clustered fibrils were visible again, resembling those at 30 mM KPi (**Figure 2C**, **iv**). Furthermore, TEM images revealed an alternative pathway leading to formation of particles, which became dominating above 150 mM KPi (**Figure**

2C, v). To sum up, eADF4(Ω 16) is able to form long, entangled, branched fibrils in the concentration regime of 50-100 mM KPi showing faster assembly kinetics than eADF4(C16). The fibrils are comparable to that of eADF4(C16) (exemplarily shown for 150 mM KPi in **Figure 2C, vi**), although the KPi regime for nucleation and fibril formation was significantly broader (10 mM-300 mM).^{11, 12, 29, 49, 50} The transition zone, where both, fibrils and particles, were observed, was shifted to 400 mM KPi in case of eADF4(C16), and particles only could be precipitated above 500 mM.^{29, 30}

Considering these findings, a sequence-dependent assembly model of eADF4-based proteins was created (**Figure 3**). Negatively charged eADF4(C16) shows high hydration and stability in aqueous buffers after dialysis out of chaotropic solvents at RT due to electrostatic repulsion, since the theoretical isoelectric point (IEP) is at 3.5. Zeta potential measurements in KCl (pH 2.5-10.0) and isoelectric focusing revealed experimental IEPs of around 3.9 and 4.5, respectively.⁶⁹

Figure 3. Impact of KPi-concentration on the self-assembly behavior of two different recombinant eADF4 variants into fibrils and particles. eADF4(Ω 16) is more sensitive towards KPi compared

to eADF4(C16)²⁹. Precipitation into particles can already be detected at a KPi concentration of 150 mM.

Since eADF4(C16) contains glutamic acid residues, it is able to form non-covalent interactions with the solvent and buffer components via its carboxyl groups and stays as an unstructured monomer in solution at RT. Thus, eADF4(C16) shows a low aggregation and slow assembly behavior in the absence of any trigger (e.g. addition of KPi or shear forces), administered by its solution stability over several weeks. eADF4(Q16) with its glutamine residues (i.e. pH-independent uncharged residue) showed time-, temperature- and concentration-dependent protein aggregation behavior in buffers with pH values between 7 and 8.^{58, 63} At RT, eADF4(Q16) precipitation was significantly accelerated, indicated by an increase in turbidity and occurrence of whitish assemblies/aggregates after several hours, even without an external trigger. Moreover, eADF4(Q16) showed lower critical solution temperature (LCST) behavior, being stabilized in solution at 4°C. A possible explanation for the pronounced aggregation of the protein without typical triggers, such as kosmotropic ions or shear forces, could be that the IEP of eADF4(Q16) with 7.7⁶⁹ is inside the selected pH range of the used buffer systems. Isoelectric focusing of eADF4(Q16) revealed an IEP between 7.8-8.3, and zeta potential measurements in KCl (pH 2.5-10.0) showed that the zeta potential was close to zero between pH 6.0 and 8.5⁶⁹. Since eADF4(Q16) is uncharged, it shows reduced non-covalent interactions with ions in aqueous buffers leading to an increase of hydrophobic protein-protein interactions and faster protein aggregation. It was shown previously that glutamic acid, aspartic acid and serine residues increase the solubility of proteins (e.g. RNase) significantly, while hydrophilic amino acids including glutamine, threonine and asparagine residues contribute unfavorably to protein solubility.⁷⁰

At self-assembly conditions (pH 7-8), the addition of kosmotropic phosphate to eADF4(C16) solutions decreases the hydration of the protein and allows a restructuring of the flexible protein backbone leading to increased intramolecular interactions.^{11, 50} Hence, the poly-alanine-stretches form stable β -sheets leading to meta-stable seeds, which interact with further soluble protein

monomers, finally directing fibril elongation.^{12, 50} With increasing KPi concentrations, the hydration decreases further, leading to enhanced intramolecular protein-protein-interactions and salting-out effects resulting in spider silk particle precipitation. Therefore, between 300 and 400 mM KPi, a transition of nanofibril to particle formation occurs, while only particles precipitate at higher salt concentrations.^{29, 30} In contrast, since eADF4(Ω 16) is uncharged at neutral pH, low to no electrostatic repulsion occurs. Therefore, less amounts of KPi are necessary to support protein restructuring and formation of hydrophobic protein interactions, leading to faster structure formation of eADF4(Ω 16), nucleation and self-assembly (**Figure 2A**). In addition, the lack of intermolecular protein repulsion made it more “salt-sensitive” shifting the transition zone from forming nanofibrils to particles from 350 mM in case of eADF4(C16) to 150 mM KPi in case of eADF4(Ω 16) (**Figure 3**). Furthermore, an alternative aggregation pathway appeared at 30 and 150 mM KPi for eADF4(Ω 16), which is not present in case of KPi-triggered eADF4(C16) assembly. Hence, we presumed differed starting conformations of both proteins, due to significant charge differences (see below).

Conformation of spider silk proteins at neutral pH

We further analyzed the soluble spider silk variants in low ionic strength buffer to gain more insights in the starting protein conformation at neutral pH. Far-UV CD-spectra confirmed that monomers of both proteins were intrinsically unstructured concerning their secondary structure in this state (after dialysis and ultracentrifugation), as observed previously^{46, 47, 50} (**Figure S2**). To confirm the hypothesis that the presence of charged amino acids influences protein conformation and, hence, inter- and intramolecular interactions during assembly events, SEC-MALS of soluble proteins was conducted (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4. SEC-MALS analyses revealed different protein conformations of eADF4(C16) and eADF4(Q16). Negatively charged eADF4(C16) showed lower retention times indicating larger hydrodynamic radii (R_H) as well as larger calculated R_g compared to the later retention times (smaller R_H) and smaller calculated R_g of the uncharged eADF4(Q16). Data were obtained from four independent measurements for each protein ($n=4$). Differences in the calculated MWs from the SEC-MALS data were caused by the uncertainty of the MALS calculations resulting from the difference in applied protein concentrations (3 mg/mL and 1 mg/mL for eADF4(C16) and eADF4(Q16), respectively). MALDI-TOF confirmed similar MWs (see **Figure S3**).

Since both proteins have the same number of amino acids ($n=576$) and similar molecular weights (MW=47.7 kDa) confirmed by MALDI-TOF analysis (**Figure S3**), an apparent difference in retention time observed for eADF4(C16) (~15 min, **Figure 4**, orange curve) and eADF4(Q16) (~15.7 min, **Figure 4**, purple curve) at the same elution conditions strongly indicated different conformational packing of the proteins. This was supported by the calculated geometric radii ($R_g=6.88$ nm for eADF4(C16) and $R_g=6.08$ nm for eADF4(Q16)). The larger geometric radius of

negatively charged eADF4(C16) resulted most probably from its intramolecular repulsion, i.e. loosely packed, unstructured conformation. In contrast, the smaller geometric radius of eADF4(Q16) points towards a more compact protein structure (**Figure 4**). Upon addition of KPi^{49, 50} or increasing protein concentrations, eADF4(C16) forms fibrils below 10 mg/mL and physically crosslinked fibrillar networks, i.e. hydrogels above 10 mg/mL.^{52, 57-63} In case of eADF4(Q16), uncharged glutamine residues allow compaction of the proteins supporting intramolecular hydrophobic interaction of poly-alanine motives. This enhances their transition into beta-sheets and, consequently, formation of nuclei towards aggregation and assembly, depending on the presence of KPi. These results are in line with a previous study showing that eADF4(Q16) is stabilized by addition of amphiphilic dimethylsulfoxid (DMSO) as co-solvent, most probably shielding the hydrophobic polyalanines and increasing the interaction with the surrounding solvent by formation of hydrogen bonds.⁵⁸

Influence of pH on eADF4 assembly and aggregation

Since charge and polarity of amino acids of the protein backbone showed impact on hydration status, colloidal stability, conformation and self-assembly of eADF4, we further analyzed assembly/aggregation behavior of eADF4(C16) and eADF4(Q16) at different pH values (pH 3-10) to gain detailed insights in (de-)protonation effects. Consecutive protonation of glutamic acid residues in eADF4(C16), i.e. its charge neutralization, transferred the behavior of this protein to an eADF4(Q16)-like one, as confirmed by turbidity kinetics at 340 nm at different pH values (**Figure 5**). The dropping pH affected solubility and self-assembly/aggregation of eADF4(C16) much stronger (**Figure 5A**) than of eADF4(Q16) (**Figure 5B**). eADF4(C16) remained soluble at a pH ≥ 6 but displayed highly accelerated assembly/aggregation at pH ≤ 5 , showing similar kinetic parameters as eADF4(Q16) (**Table S1B**) most probably due to its low pI. Extensive protonation of the glutamic acid residues led to a charge distribution resembling uncharged eADF4(Q16) with its glutamine residues. The importance of charges is stressed in the behavior of eADF4(Q16),

being substantially less sensitive to pH changes in comparison to eADF4(C16) and showing similar assembly/aggregation kinetics between pH 3 and 9 (**Figure 5B** and **Table S1B**).

Figure 5. Analysis of the pH-dependent assembly/aggregation behavior of eADF4 variants. Turbidity measurements at 340 nm indicated pH-dependent assembly kinetics for eADF4(C16) (**A**) and pH-independent kinetics for eADF4(Ω 16) (**B**). FTIR-spectra of assembled protein species showed β -sheet rich assemblies for eADF4(C16) (**C**) as well as for eADF4(Ω 16) (**D**). For comparison, FTIR spectra of the protein fibrils formed in the presence of KPi at pH 8 (150 mM and 100 mM for eADF4(C16) and eADF4(Ω 16), respectively, were included as well. **E**) TEM images revealed mostly fibril assembly of eADF4(C16) at pH 3 and pH 5 as well as of eADF4(Ω 16) at pH 8.

To confirm the role of protein charge as well as of the presence of soluble protein (after dialysis), we induced additional charges on tyrosine residues by increasing the pH above a value of 8. For eADF4(Ω 16), the assembly/aggregation kinetics of eADF4(Ω 16) were slowed down at pH 10 (**Figure 5B**). Since eADF4(C16) was stable in solutions at pH \geq 6 (**Figure 5A**), we analyzed the self-assembly kinetics at higher pH values (pH 8-10) in presence of 150 mM KPi to induce fibril formation (**Figure S1**). In this context, differences in assembly kinetics are solely influenced by the changing pH value, as phosphate is mainly 2-fold negatively charged between pH 7 and 12⁷¹. At pH 10, the kinetics showed a significant extension of the lag time (5-fold), i.e. slower formation of oligomers, whereas fibril growth kinetics (elongation phase) were more similar to those at pH 8 and 9 (2-fold increase) (**Figure S1** and **Table S1C**). Studies based on molecular modeling, NMR- and photometric titrations demonstrated that tyrosine residues, and their specific location within repetitive modules (including motifs like GPGGY found in eADF-variants), are indicators of a pre-structured state in solution.⁷² It is speculated that pre-structuring, driven by π - π stacking and CH/ π interactions, promotes the formation of beta-sheet structures during assembly.⁷³⁻⁷⁵ However, in solutions with a pH of 10, spider silk proteins based on ADF4 sequences contained solvent-exposed tyrosine residues (pKa \sim 10) due to partial negative charges.⁷⁵⁻⁷⁷ Hence, deprotonation diminishes tyrosine-based intramolecular interactions of the eADF4-variants at pH 10. Therefore, an opening of the structure is allowed, which is reducing the probability of hydrophobic

intermolecular interactions and beta-sheet formation based thereon, i.e. inhibits to some extent nucleus formation.

For both eADF4-based variants, the protein assemblies at different pH values were analyzed using FTIR spectroscopy and Fourier-Self-Deconvolution (FSD) of the amide I band ⁶⁸ to determine secondary structure content (**Figure 5 C-D, Table S3, Figure S4, Figure S5**). The symmetrical peak of eADF4(C16) at 1650 cm⁻¹ indicated mainly random coil secondary structure at pH 8 (**Figure 5C**, lilac curve), as verified by FSD (**Table S3, Figure S4**). In contrast, the amide I bands of assemblies formed at pH 3 and pH 5 showed maxima at 1630 cm⁻¹ and appeared overlapping with the spectrum of nanofibrils classically formed in the presence of 150 mM KPi at pH 8 (**Figure 5C**). FSD-analysis also confirmed an increased β -sheet content (> 40 %) of eADF4(C16) assemblies at pH 3, pH 5 and in presence of 150 mM KPi, while random coil and α -helices were decreased compared to soluble eADF4(C16) at pH 8 (**Table S3, Figure S4**).

Similar results were observed for eADF4(Ω 16) (**Figure 5D, Table S3, Figure S5**). At pH 8 (**Figure 5D**, purple curve), eADF4(Ω 16) also exhibited mainly random coil secondary structure after ultracentrifugation, as indicated by the symmetrical peak at 1650 cm⁻¹ and confirmed by FSD analysis (**Table S3, Figure S5**). In addition, asymmetrical amide I bands of assemblies formed at pH 3, pH 5 and pH 10 exhibited their maxima at around 1630 cm⁻¹ and appeared overlapping with the spectrum of nanofibrils formed in the presence of 100 mM KPi at pH 8 (**Figure 5D**). FSD-analysis verified an increased β -sheet content (> 39 %) of eADF4(Ω 16) assemblies at pH 3, pH 5, pH 10 and in the presence of 100 mM KPi, with the maximum β -sheet value for fibrils formed in 100 mM KPi, while random coil structures and α -helices were decreased compared to soluble eADF4(Ω 16) at pH 8 (**Table S3, Figure S5**). However, the more pronounced shoulders around 1650 cm⁻¹, in comparison to eADF4(C16) in **Figure 5C**, also refer to higher random coil and α -helical content, as confirmed by FSD (**Table S3, Figure S5**). Interestingly, at pH 8, soluble eADF4(C16) displayed a significantly lower β -sheet content (14 %) than eADF4(Ω 16) (23 %, **Table S3**). Hence, the simultaneous increase in β -sheet content and decrease in random coil

structure confirmed the enhanced pre-structuring and compaction of eADF4(Ω 16) at pH 8 in comparison to the more loosely packed and unstructured eADF4(C16) already seen in SEC-MALS (**Figure 4**), which is responsible for accelerated fibril formation and aggregation of eADF4(Ω 16).

The morphology of eADF4-based assemblies formed at different pH-values was analyzed using TEM enabling the distinction between guided assembly into nanofibrils and uncontrolled protein aggregation. TEM images revealed that the β -sheet-rich eADF4(C16)-assemblies at lower pH-values (pH 3 and 5) were mainly ordered fibrils and their conglomerates, and only few, bulky aggregates (**Figure 5E**, i-ii). Therefore, no additional kosmotropic phosphate ions are necessary to induce fibril formation below pH 5. However, eADF4(C16) fibril length decreases with dropping pH. The reason could be the occurrence of accompanying aggregation depleting the monomers' availability for fibril growth as well as the increase of nucleation events, i.e. more docking sites for eADF4(C16) monomers. TEM images also verified that eADF4(Ω 16) assembles into ordered fibrils, as exemplarily shown for samples harvested at pH 8 without addition of KPi (**Figure 5E**, iii), whereas eADF4(C16) stayed soluble under these conditions. In this context, the morphology and length of eADF4(C16) fibrils at pH 3 (**Figure 5E**, i) and eADF4(Ω 16) fibrils at pH 8 (**Figure 5E**, iii) likely resemble, since both proteins showed identical net charge and accelerated nucleation and assembly behavior under these conditions.

Taken together, the pH-dependent aggregation analysis of eADF4(C16) and eADF4(Ω 16) confirmed the conclusions drawn by analyzing the SEC-MALS data, and displayed that eADF4(Ω 16) is already pre-structured, shows a similar charge distribution and high level of restructuring at all investigated pH-values due to intra- and intermolecular interactions. In contrast, eADF4(C16) is deprotonated, soluble and elongated above neutral pH and needs external triggers, such as pH-drop or kosmotropic phosphate, to initiate conformational changes.

Based on these results and in addition to the previous sequence-dependent model, a pH-dependent structure and self-assembly model for eADF4(C16) and eADF4(Ω 16) has been developed (**Figure 6**) highlighting the correlation of pH, charge and protein conformation. In general, a pH-drop and

the associated protonation and change in charge influence the conformation of eADF4(C16) much stronger than that of the uncharged eADF4(Ω 16). Above physiological pH, eADF4(C16) shows high solubility and an expanded, less compact structure due to electrostatic repulsion of the glutamic acid residues in the repetitive modules of the protein backbone. With decreasing pH, an increased restructuring and compaction of eADF4(C16) occurred due to increased protonation and decreased electrostatic repulsion.

Figure 6. Schematic model of the protein conformation of eADF4(C16) and eADF4(Ω 16) at different pH-values explaining the different assembly behavior due to deprotonation of tyrosine residues resulting the increase of negative charges.

Below the IEP of eADF4(C16) (IEP=3.5), the complete loss of electrostatic repulsion led to maximum compaction of monomeric eADF4(C16) resulting in accelerated assembly/aggregation.

Due to the complete protonation of the carboxyl groups at pH 3 and the accompanying loss of

charges, the strong hydration and solvent interaction of eADF4(C16) is suddenly diminished. Combined with the removal of electrostatic repulsion, the protein backbone collapses and restructures quickly leading to enhanced intramolecular protein-protein-interactions accelerating self-assembly and aggregation. In contrast, uncharged eADF4(Ω 16) has time to get accustomed to a polar solvent during dialysis. Thus, pH-changes don't affect hydration and conformational state. Therefore, conformation and assembly/aggregation behavior of eADF4(Ω 16) are scarcely influenced by pH-shifts, as there are no significant changes in (de-) protonation or protein charge. This uncharged protein consistently shows a compacted protein structure causing a continuous assembly/aggregation based on hydrophobic interactions over a wide pH-range. However, the deprotonation of tyrosine residues (two per repetitive C-/ Ω -module) at pH 10 introduces local negative charges, which increase the hydration status, the interaction with the solvent and the electrostatic repulsion of the protein backbone. Thus, the structure of eADF4(Ω 16) is not strictly compacted anymore, resulting in decelerated restructuring and less intramolecular protein-protein interactions leading to less nucleation events as well as decreased assembly rates and fibril growth.

Conclusion and Outlook

We could show that single amino acid exchanges within the eADF4 consensus sequence strongly influence protein conformation and stability of the spider silk variants eADF4(C16) and eADF4(Ω 16) in solution as well as their self-assembly and rate of fibril formation (**Figure 7**). We identified that protein restructuring and guided fibril formation could be controlled and scaled by adopting external conditions including the concentration of kosmotropic phosphate or the pH-value, but their influence differs significantly between both proteins. We could show that the exchange of negatively charged amino acids (glutamic acid residues) to uncharged equivalents (glutamine ones) altered solubility and conformation at physiological pH from a completely soluble, loosely packed, elongated state (eADF4(C16)), to a pre-structured, compacted state (eADF4(Ω 16)), respectively, as well as the sensitivity towards kosmotropic phosphate and pH-shifts (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Identification of optimal conditions for recombinant spider silk processing. By unravelling critical stimuli influencing recombinant spider silk protein assembly, processing conditions for spider silk materials could be optimized and adjusted.

Our results indicated that the pre-structuring of eADF4(Q16) monomers led to a shortened lag phase of fibril assembly indicating faster primary nucleation and a higher number of β -sheet-rich seeds. However, deprotonation of tyrosine residues at pH 10, and, thus, introduction of partial negative charges decreases hydrophobic interactions and restructuring. Therefore, our results expand the possibilities of processing artificial proteins in a targeted manner for specific purposes and applications (**Figure 7**). The processing conditions have to be protein-specifically adjusted, since the processing parameters could significantly differ after exchanging even as little as just one amino acid in the repetitive module. Furthermore, since nanofibrils are also a route towards (hydro-)gel networks, an adept knowledge of processing conditions and self-assembly kinetics could increase guided nucleation, assembly, and thus, gelation speed. The optimal gel formation is highly important for the generation of cell-laden gels and bioinks. A fast gelation process ensures

optimal cell distribution inside the silk scaffolds as well as high survival of encapsulated cells^{52, 59, 61, 62}. In conclusion, this study nicely displayed, how protein design and engineering could influence spider silk protein properties and self-assembly behavior, and how it allows for an optimized, controllable and scalable processing of silk materials for technical or biomedical applications, tissue engineering, and biofabrication.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the ACS Online Library.

Rate constants and lag times of kinetic measurements, secondary structure contents of recombinant spider silk assemblies, pH-influence on self-assembly kinetics in presence of 150 mM KPi, CD-spectra of spider silk proteins, Maldi-Tof-spectra of spider silk proteins, and FSD-analysis of spider silk proteins and assemblies at different pH-values.

Author Contributions

Vanessa T. Trossmann: Conceptualization, investigation, formal analysis; writing – original draft; **Veronika Hovanová:** Conceptualization, investigation; formal analysis; writing, reviewing & editing the draft; **Tim Schiller:** Investigation; formal analysis; reviewing & editing the draft; **Martin Humenik:** Conceptualization; formal analysis; funding acquisition; reviewing & editing the draft; supervision; **Erik Sedlák:** Funding acquisition; reviewing & editing the draft, supervision; **Thomas R. Scheibel:** Conceptualization; funding acquisition; reviewing & editing the draft; supervision.

Conflict of Interest

Thomas R. Scheibel is co-founder and shareholder of AMSilk GmbH. The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Graphical Abstract

